

Manipur's Ethnic Divide: Inside the Meitei-Kuki Conflict

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Abstract: This study examines the ethnic conflict between the Meitei and Kuki-Chin-Mizo communities in Manipur, focusing on the violent outbreak of May 3, 2023. Manipur, once known for its cultural diversity and relative harmony, has seen its inter-community relations strained by growing ethnic nationalism, competing political ambitions, and territorial disputes. The Meitei demand for Scheduled Tribe (ST) status, government actions against illegal migration and poppy cultivation, and marginalization of tribal communities have further intensified tensions. Using qualitative methods and secondary sources, this research analyses the historical roots, socio-political dynamics, and immediate causes of the conflict. The study concludes that lasting peace requires inclusive dialogue among all stakeholders, equitable hill–valley development, effective management of illegal immigration, and negotiated solutions to sensitive issues such as poppy eradication and ST demands. Long-term peacebuilding must also foster inter-ethnic trust through education, cultural exchange, and inclusive political representation to ensure justice and coexistence in Manipur.

Keywords: Ethnic Conflict, Meitei-Kuki Relations, Manipur Violence, Inter-Ethnic Relations, Peace building

Introduction

Manipur, a beautiful and captivating state in northeastern India, is renowned for its breathtaking landscapes, vibrant art form, and a rich culture. Though small in size, Manipur has made a name for itself globally, producing top tier sportspersons and playing a vital role in enriching nation's cultural and athletic heritage. Often referred to as the "Jewel of India," it offers a unique experience of diverse ethnic communities, where hills and valleys, along with their various languages, traditions, and customs blend to form a vibrant cultural legacy.

1.1. Ethnic Composition and Regional Dynamics of Manipur

Manipur is inhabited by three major ethnic communities the Meitei, the Nagas, and the Kuki-Chin-Mizo tribes. The state's geography is distinctly divided into two regions: the central valley and the surrounding

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hills. While the valley constitutes roughly 10% of Manipur's total land area, the hills encompass the remaining 90% (Directorate of Economic & Statistics Government of Manipur Lamphelpat, 2021).

The Meitei, who form the majority population, predominantly reside in the valley region, while the surrounding hill areas are home to a diverse range of tribal groups. These hill communities are generally classified into two major ethnic categories: the Nagas and the Kuki-Chin-Mizo groups. Traditionally, these three communities shared a history of coexistence and mutual cultural exchange, contributing to the rich and diverse heritage of the state.

Supporting this view, Senjam (1996) highlights two traditional sayings *Chingburoi Tamburoi* and *Haoringjel Nairingjel* which reflect the dual nature of the past relationship between the hills and plains. The first conveys sentiments of love, friendship, and mutual understanding, while the second suggests elements of distrust and animosity. However, S. Mangi emphasizes that the relationship was predominantly shaped by *Chingburoi Tamburoi*, symbolizing trust and mutual respect. Similarly, Gangte (2013) argues that the Meiteis, Nagas, and Kukis, despite their distinct identities, share common origins, as seen in their historical cohabitation, political evolution, and cultural exchanges.

However, despite this historical harmony, underlying differences in identity, territory, and political aspirations have occasionally surfaced, creating friction in inter-community relationships. Their long-standing ties are now challenged by competing demands and changing socio-political dynamics (Lourembam, 2025).

Over time, the Meitei, Naga, and Kuki-Chin-Mizo communities in Manipur have developed divergent socio-political aspirations, which have increasingly come into conflict with one another. The Meiteis primarily emphasize preserving the territorial integrity and unity of the state. In contrast, the Nagas seek the unification of all Naga-inhabited areas across state and national boundaries into a single political entity often referred to as "Greater Nagalim." On the other hand, the Kuki-Chin-Mizo groups are pushing for the creation of a separate administrative arrangement that would grant them greater autonomy and recognition.

These aspirations are inherently incompatible, as none of the hill regions in Manipur are inhabited exclusively by any single ethnic group. The Naga demand for integration creates anxiety among the Kuki-Zo-Mizo communities, who fear marginalization and loss of land, while the Meitei community worries about further territorial fragmentation and the erosion of the state's integrity. Similarly, the call for a separate administrative setup by the Kuki-Chin-Mizo tribes is seen as a threat to the Meitei vision of a united and undivided Manipur, while the Naga community views it as potentially undermining their own

demand for integration of Naga-inhabited areas (Lourembam, 2025). These competing visions of identity, autonomy, and territory have led to increasing tensions and a breakdown of inter-ethnic trust and cooperation.

1.2. Fragile Inter-Community Relations

Ethnic conflicts are a common feature in multi-ethnic societies, where differing identities, interests, and historical grievances often collide. Manipur, with its complex mosaic of ethnic communities, remains particularly prone to such tensions and confrontations. The state's social fabric has witnessed repeated fractures, especially during the last decade of the twentieth century, which was marked by several violent ethnic clashes. The most prominent among them was the Naga-Kuki conflict, which ranged from 1992 to 1998 and led to widespread violence and displacement. In 1993, tensions escalated between the Meiteis and the Muslim community, resulting in violent confrontations. This was followed by a clash between the Kukis and Tamils in the border town of Moreh in 1995. Subsequently, the Kuki-Paite conflict erupted between 1997 and 1998, further deepening ethnic divisions (Singh, 2006).

These conflicts reflected long-standing grievances over land, identity, representation, and access to resources. Each episode of violence not only resulted in loss of lives and property but also hardened community boundaries and eroded trust. More recently, in 2023, the Meitei-Kuki conflict broke out, becoming one of the most intense and tragic instances of ethnic violence in Manipur's recent history. This pattern of recurring violence underscores the fragile nature of inter-ethnic relations in the state and highlights the urgent need for sustained peacebuilding efforts, inclusive dialogue, and political solutions that acknowledge the aspirations of all communities.

2. Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative approach to examine the complex dynamics of the Kuki-Meitei Conflict in Manipur, focusing on the historical, social, and political factors leading to the 2023 violence. It relies primarily on secondary sources, including scholarly books, peer-reviewed articles, government reports, and credible news coverage, to provide a balanced understanding of the conflict's causes and progression. A contextual and thematic analysis is used to identify recurring grievances, patterns of discrimination, and community perceptions.

3. Meitei and Kuki ethnic Conflict

3.1. The Outbreak of Violence on May 3, 2023

On May 3, 2023, an intense ethnic conflict broke out in Churachandpur district, Manipur, involving the Meitei and Kuki-Chin-Mizo communities. The violence erupted during a solidarity march organized by the All-Tribal Students' Union Manipur (ATSUM) as a protest against the Manipur High Court's directive to the state government to recommend the Meitei community's inclusion in the Scheduled Tribe (ST) list. The protest, which reflected widespread opposition to the Meitei demand for ST status, triggered counter-blockades by some valley-based groups. What began as a march soon escalated into widespread violence, including gunfire on the streets of Churachandpur, where armed groups reportedly used advanced weapons. Numerous reports emerged of Meitei homes being burned in Torbung and nearby areas, which are predominantly inhabited by Kukis. In response, sections of the Meitei community initially tried to defend their localities, but the situation soon spiralled out of control, leading to retaliatory actions against Kuki settlements in the valley and foothill areas. This resulted in further arson, destruction of property, and displacement of civilians, thereby escalating the conflict to unprecedented levels and drawing in wider participation from both Meitei and Kuki communities. The unrest led to a tragic loss of lives and large-scale displacement. Thousands of homes were destroyed, and religious sites, including temples and churches, were vandalized and set ablaze. Many people sustained injuries, and several were reported missing. As noted by Shimrah (2023), the extent of brutality was unprecedented, revealing the deeply entrenched animosity between the two communities.

3.2. Understanding the Roots of Manipur's Ethnic Conflict

To gain a deeper and more comprehensive understanding of the ongoing ethnic conflict in Manipur, it is essential to examine the historical ethnic divisions and the broader underlying causes that have shaped current tensions. Ethnic conflicts, by nature, are complex and fluid phenomena. They do not arise from a single issue or event but are instead the result of multiple, interwoven factors that evolve over time. Each conflict has its own specific historical, social, political, and economic dimensions, making it unique in its origin and manifestation. Manipur is no exception to this rule.

In the context of Manipur, ethnic conflicts have demonstrated a particularly dynamic character. The state's multi-ethnic composition and history of political fragmentation mean that the causes of conflict are rarely static. Instead, they vary according to changing political developments, shifting alliances, economic disparities, and perceptions of identity and representation among the different ethnic groups. Despite this

complexity, there are certain overarching and recurring issues that have contributed to the persistence of conflict across time.

3.3. Broad Underlying Causes of Ethnic Clashes in Manipur

These general underlying causes include historical grievances over land ownership and access to resources, uneven development between the hill and valley regions, political marginalization of certain communities, and the growth of competing ethno-nationalist movements. Such conditions have bred mistrust and competition, and they continue to fuel ongoing tensions. Understanding these root causes is crucial, as it provides a foundation for analysing not just the surface-level triggers of violence, but also the deeper structural and historical issues that must be addressed in any long-term resolution strategy.

The reasons for the ethnic violence in Manipur can be traced to a complex interplay of historical, socioeconomic, and political factors that have unfolded over decades. These tensions are deeply rooted in longstanding grievances and clashing aspirations among the various ethnic communities that inhabit the state. Manipur's inter-ethnic relations have always been layered and multifaceted, shaped by divergent identities, cultural differences, and competing political narratives. A key element contributing to the unrest is the uneven development between the hill areas and the valley region. The hill communities, in particular, have often expressed a strong sense of being marginalized and excluded from the mainstream political and economic processes of the state. This perception stems from limited infrastructure, inadequate access to education and health services, and a lack of political representation.

The exclusionary development pattern has created a significant divide between the communities, with many in the hill districts feeling alienated and left behind in the state's overall progress. This growing resentment among hill dwellers has intensified their grievances and added fuel to inter-community distrust and dissatisfaction. Additionally, the emergence and spread of micro-nationalism in the region have further complicated the situation. As various ethnic groups have become increasingly assertive about their unique identities, histories, and rights to land and self-governance, competition for territorial and political claims has escalated.

This rise in ethnic assertion has coincided with the proliferation of armed insurgent groups and ethnically aligned factions, each advocating for their own political objectives and territorial ambitions. Over the decades, these groups have entrenched divisions by promoting exclusive narratives and demanding separate homelands, which has significantly undermined efforts toward communal harmony and peaceful

coexistence. Collectively, these factors have created a volatile and deeply fragmented socio-political environment, making the conflict both enduring and difficult to resolve (Meitei, 2023).

4. Key Factors Intensifying Meitei–Kuki conflict

4.1.Immediate Triggers and Heightened Meitei–Kuki Tensions

The immediate cause of the conflict may have been the High Court’s directive to the Manipur government and the subsequent peace march. However, tensions between the Meitei and Kuki communities had been building for some time. They should be understood in the context of several interconnected issues. These include the illegal influx of migrants, the War on Drugs, the government’s strict policies against poppy cultivation in forest areas, and the Meitei community’s demand for Scheduled Tribe (ST) status. These tensions were further fuelled by resentment within the Kuki community, which viewed the state government as Meitei-dominated and perceived its policies as anti-Kuki, anti-tribal, anti-minority, and anti-Christian (Shimrah, 2023). In the months leading up to the violence, certain government actions were also seen by the Kuki community as discriminatory, heightening their sense of insecurity.

4.2.Illegal Migration and Land Encroachment

Amid these growing grievances and mutual suspicions, another critical factor deepening the divide was the issue of illegal migration and its impact on land and resources. The influx of illegal migrants from Myanmar into Manipur has raised concerns among the Meitei and other tribes about the coexistence of indigenous communities. The Meitei community strongly opposed the Kuki's encroachment on forest land and the rapid establishment of new villages in the foothills of Imphal Valley, leading to confrontations over land disputes in areas like the Kobrou Hill Range, Thangjing Hill, and other foothill regions (Shimrah, 2023). Chief Minister Biren Singh’s government claimed that illegal migration was a pressing issue and took actions such as detaining hundreds of illegal migrants and suspending the Free Movement Regime with Myanmar. These measures angered the Kuki community, deepening their sense of marginalization and intensifying tensions. The identification of alleged intruders and subsequent eviction orders further fuelled the conflict, as forced evictions led to clashes between villagers and authorities. The Kuki community perceived the government's actions as being directed at them due to their affinity with refugees from Myanmar. The government countered these allegations by claiming that out of 291 encroachers removed between 2017 and 2023, 160 were Meitei, suggesting that Kukis were not exclusively targeted. Despite this, the Kuki community feels disproportionately affected, fuelling their discontent (Das, 2023).

4.3. War on Drugs, withdrawal of Peace Agreement, and Rising Tensions

Another major issue was the Government's war on drugs campaign in 2017, where the Manipur War on Drugs campaign fought against illegal poppy cultivation in the hill districts. The Kuki community was disproportionately affected as they had more land under poppy cultivation. The destruction of poppy fields and arrests were viewed as threats to their livelihood, escalating tensions. It provoked widespread protests, particularly in Kuki-dominated areas; some turned violent—for instance, the April 27, 2023 protest in Churachandpur. The state government described these protests as anti-government. It blamed Kuki militant groups, including the KNA and ZRA, for fanning unrest and sheltering illegal migrants and drug trafficking.

Earlier, on March 10, 2023, the Government led by Biren Singh unilaterally withdrew from the tripartite Suspension of Operations (SoO) agreement with Kuki militant groups, causing the Kukis to react in anger and raising questions on the peace negotiations going ahead. (Das, 2023). These developments further deepened mistrust and heightened the sense of insecurity within the Kuki community, adding yet another layer of tension to the already fragile inter-ethnic relations

4.4. The Meitei Demand for Scheduled Tribe Status

Another significant contentious point in the conflict is the demand for Schedule Tribe by the Meitei community. The demand for Scheduled Tribe (ST) status by the Meitei community is based on their claim that they are the original inhabitants of Manipur. The flooding and assimilation of outsiders threaten their land, culture, and identity. They claim that granting them ST status will help to preserve their language, customs, culture, and ancestral territory. However, tribal opposition to this idea stems from the Meiteis' predominance in socio-political spheres as they feel it will undermine their political representation, threaten their land rights, and diminish the benefits of their reserved status. They perceive the demand as a danger to their existence and an attempt by the Meiteis to seize more control over the state. (Meitei, 2023).

Taken together, these interconnected issues reveal that the violence in Manipur is not the result of a single trigger but a culmination of layered grievances, competing identities, and perceived injustices. Each factor whether it is the Meitei demand for ST status, the crackdown on poppy cultivation, the handling of illegal migration, or land encroachment has amplified mistrust and hardened ethnic divisions. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for shaping meaningful dialogue and crafting solutions that address both the immediate and structural causes of the conflict.

5. Conclusion

The Manipur ethnic conflict underscores how historical grievances, competing political aspirations, and socio-economic disparities create enduring tensions in a multi-ethnic society. While the immediate trigger for the 2023 violence was the Meitei demand for Scheduled Tribe status, the roots of the crisis lie in deeper structural issues. Uneven development between the hill and valley regions, contested claims over land and resources, and unresolved challenges like illegal migration have long fuelled mistrust. The War on Drugs campaign, which disproportionately affected the hill areas, further aggravated feelings of marginalization and injustice.

These issues have been compounded by strong ethno-nationalist sentiments. The presence of ethnically aligned militant groups and competing territorial aspirations has fragmented social cohesion, making reconciliation and durable peace difficult. Addressing this conflict requires a multi-pronged approach. First, inclusive dialogue must bring together all stakeholders—Meiteis, Kukis, Nagas, civil society, and state and central governments. Second, policies ensuring equitable development between hills and valley are essential to reduce socio-economic disparities. This includes better infrastructure, access to education, healthcare, and economic opportunities for all. Third, managing illegal immigration with stronger border control, modern surveillance, and proper identity checks is crucial. Verified refugees should be accommodated in temporary shelters, while land and forest laws must be enforced transparently. Fourth, sensitive issues such as poppy eradication, insurgency, and the demand for ST status should be resolved through negotiated settlements, ensuring all voices are heard. Finally, long-term peacebuilding must focus on fostering inter-ethnic trust through education, cultural exchange, and inclusive political representation. Recognizing the legitimacy of each community's fears and aspirations is key to building coexistence, justice, and lasting peace in Manipur.

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